

**NETWORK PHARMACOLOGY AND EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF THE
THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF *HYGROPHILA SCHULLI* (KOKILAKSHA) SEEDS
IN THE TREATMENT OF HYPERLIPIDEMIA**

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda attributes the pain-relieving, anti-inflammatory, and rejuvenating (Rasayana) properties of *Hygrophila schulli* (Kokilaksha), belonging to the family Acanthaceae. Despite used for enhancing energy and vitality, its effects on obesity and lipid levels remain insufficiently researched in the scientific literature. Ayurvedic treatise is a vital source of energy and strength. For Network pharmacology study various databases like Dr. Dukes, PubChem, Gene Cards and IMPPAT were utilised which identify the potential targets and related pathways. The STRING 11.5, KEGG Pathway database and Cytoscape 3.9.1 were utilised in the network pharmacology study for identifying protein targets, potential interactions, pathway analysis and for the construction of the network. Molecular docking simulations were conducted using Auto Dock Vina to investigate potential binding interactions between identified *Hygrophila schulli* compounds and key lipid metabolism regulatory proteins. Hyperlipidemia was induced by giving high fat diet along with seed extracts; blood cholesterol, HDL, triglycerides, and liver lipids were subsequently measured. In network pharmacology 779 unique targets of 37 bioactives of HS seeds were overlapped with 35 hyperlipidaemia targets using the VENN Bioinformatics Tools to obtain 7 intersecting targets (APOB, LDLR, GCG, PPARA, ABCB1, NOS3, and ADRB2). In Hyperlipidemic animals triglyceride and cholesterol levels significantly decreased when the extracts were administered, but HDL significantly increased with the hexane extract. Hepatic lipid builds up was successfully inhibited by both extracts. The study shows the strong antihyperlipidemic potential of *H. schulli* seeds, with the hexane extract showing superior efficacy by raising HDL and reducing hepatic fat deposition. These findings encourage more research on *H. schulli* as a natural treatment for metabolic diseases including hyperlipidemia.

KEYWORDS: Network Pharmacology, *Hygrophila schulli*, Kokilaksha, Hypocholesteremia, Antihyperlipidemic, ADME, System Biology

Running Title: Antiobesity evaluation of Kokilaksha

1. INTRODUCTION

Hyperlipidemia is lipid metabolism disorder with noticeable rise in triacylglycerol (TG), total cholesterol (TC), low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) and a decline in high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) in the peripheral blood. It is foremost vascular threat contributing to hypertension, diabetes, and obesity. With the modern lifestyle changes and rising lifespan, the prevalence of hyperlipidemia continues to increase each year[1].

Hyperlipidemia has been predicted as a significant contributor of cardiovascular and cerebrovascular events worldwide, highlighting the prerequisite for its prevention and management to alleviate the chances of stroke and myocardial infarction (MI)[2]. World Health Organization (WHO), reported that cardiovascular diseases (CVD) cause approximately 17.9 million deaths annually, with hyperlipidemia being a major contributing factor [3]. Although current antihyperlipidemic therapies including statins and fibrates, are effective, chronic use of these is in the majority of cases constrained by side effects, such as myopathy, liver damage, and diabetes, nephrotoxicity and neurotoxicity of statins[4]. This necessitates the investigation of other, less toxic, natural substitutes for lipid level regulation. Referring to the likely implications of hyperlipidemia and the associated adverse events of the currently used antihyperlipidemic agents, hyperlipidemic patients opt for supplementary traditional herbal medicine therapy. Safety profile, easy accessibility, affordability and environmental sustainability makes herbal medicines a choice of therapy[5]. Recently it has been reported that traditional medicine comprising of herbs and food supplements containing, vitamins, flavonoids, alkaloids, saponin, sterols, fibers and antioxidants can improve metabolic disorders like hyperlipidaemia through, inhibition low-density lipoprotein oxidation, neutralizing oxidative stress, and also via modulation of the immunity[6,7].

Hygrophila schulli (Kokilaksha), an extensively employed Ayurveda medicinal herb, is valued for its hepatoprotective, diuretic, and anti-inflammatory activities. *H. schulli* whole plant is known to exhibit various pharmacological activities viz, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, hepatoprotective, anticancer, antibacterial, antifungal, and anti-nociceptive activities[8,9,10]. In Ayurveda, *H. schulli* leaves and young stems are most commonly used for edema, inflammation, cough, bacterial infections, dysentery, joint pains, rheumatism, gout, diabetes, renal calculi and other renal diseases, hepatic diseases, microbial infections such as gonorrhoea and urinary tract infections, etc. [11]. The main bioactives present in *H. schulli* are alkaloids, glycosides, isoflavone, lupeol, stigmasterol and uncharacterized bases etc. [12,13].

Network pharmacology (NP) facilitates the understanding of multi-target interactions by mapping compound–target–disease networks, capturing the complex polypharmacological nature of drugs and herbal medicines. This systems-based method provides broader and more dependable insights than single-target pharmacology, as it accounts for synergistic effects across multiple pathways rather than isolated targets. As a result, NP enhances predictions of therapeutic efficacy, adverse effects, and drug-repurposing opportunities, particularly for complex multifactorial diseases. Hence, considering the traditional claims and phytochemical profile of *Hygrophila schulli* the present study aim to evaluate the therapeutic potential of *Hygrophila schulli* (Kokilaksha) seeds in the treatment of hyperlipidemia using in-silico Network Pharmacology approach followed by in vivo experimental validation.

2. Objectives:

This study aimed to explore the mechanism of action of *Hygrophila Schulli* in the treatment of Hyperlipidemia using network pharmacology. To investigate the antihyperlipidemic and anti-obesity potential of hexane and ethanolic seed extracts of *Hygrophila schulli* in Wistar Albino rats. A high-fat diet–induced obesity model and Triton X-100–induced hyperlipidemia

these two experimental models were used for this purpose. The effects of the extracts on lipid profiles in hyperlipidemic rats were evaluated.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material and extraction

HS seedswere collected from the surroundings of Pune, and was authenticated from Botanical survey of India, Pune (*V No. Kannur 1*). The specimen was preserved in the repository.

Extraction

Hygrophila schulli(HS) seedswere size reduced and were further extracted with 95% Ethanol and Hexane separately using Soxhlet apparatus. Hexane (HSH) and Ethanolic (HSE) extracts of HS seeds were concentrated using Rota evaporator under vacuum.

Qualitative Phytochemical Screening

Hexane (HSH) and ethanolic (HSE) extracts of HS seeds were qualitatively analysed for the presence of various phytoconstituents [14].

Data mining for bio actives of HS seedsand hyperlipidaemia targets

The datasets used in this study are all extracted from publicly available and carefully maintained databases. The datasets are FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) compliant using persistent URLs gene identifiers, and clear inclusion criteria.

The bioactive compounds present in HS seeds were obtained from Dr. Duke's Phytochemical and Ethnobotanical Database, the Indian Medicinal Plants, Phytochemistry and Therapeutics (IMPPAT) database v2.0 (available at IMPPAT | IMPPAT: Indian Medicinal Plants, Phytochemistry And Therapeutics,accessed Mar 2025) and relevant literature sources [8,13]. The canonical SMILES and PubChem CID of each bioactive were retrieved from the PubChem database.The potential protein targets of these bioactive compounds were predicted using the SwissTargetPrediction12.0 web tool (available at <http://www.swisstargetprediction.ch/>, accessed on Mar 2025) [15,16].Proteins involved in the pathogenesis of hyperlipidemia were retrieved from two databases: DisGeNET Available at DISGENET: The most complete genomics platform - Home, accessed on Mar 2025), and STRING database Version 11.5 (Available at <https://string-db.org/>, accessed on Mar2025)[16,17].The Venny 2.0 was utilized to analyze the common targets between disease and phytocompound targets.

The predicted targets of HSbioactives were then overlapped with these hyperlipidemia-associated targets to identify *Hygrophila schulli* -specific hyperlipidemia-related targets (HS-HL).

Network Construction and Analysis

A protein-protein interaction (PPI) network of the identified hyperlipidemia-related targets was constructed using the STRING database Version 12.0(Available at <https://string-db.org/>, accessed on Mar 2025) [17].The minimum required interaction score was 0.4 (medium confidence).FDR cut off set to 0.05 to include top 10 pathways.

Active interaction sources included curated databases, experiments, co-expression, and text mining. Isolated nodes were hidden to enhance network robustness.

Additionally, a network comprising HSbioactives, their predicted targets, and hyperlipidemia-related targets, along with associated KEGG pathways, was constructed and analysed using Cytoscape version 3.9.1 (Available atCytoscape Web,accessed on March 2025 [16,18].

Furthermore, KEGG pathway enrichment analysis was performed using ShinyGoverion 0.77 Available atShinyGO 0.77, accessed on March 2025)to identify pathways significantly associated with the candidate targets, providing insights into the molecular mechanisms underlying the therapeutic potential of HSin hyperlipidemia.

Docking methodology

Molecular docking analysis was performed to predict the binding affinity using AutoDockVina version 1.2.0,(accessed on March 2026)to evaluate the interaction patterns.

ADME analysis

Using the SwissADME online program(available at <http://www.swissadme.ch>, accessed on March 2026), the absorption, distribution metabolism, excretion (ADME) characteristics of bioactives were predicted. Bioactives canonical SMILES was obtained from the PubChem database, and submitted to the SwissADME service for examination. The platform evaluates physicochemical properties such as lipophilicity, pharmacokinetic behavior, water solubility, medicinal chemistry suitability and drug-likeness. The oral bioavailability and pharmacokinetic feasibility of bioactives were evaluated using the expected ADME properties which were created using default settings.SwissTarget identifies the top 100 putative targets with a probability above zero, resulting in a focused yet comprehensive set of high-likelihood targets for subsequent network pharmacology and experimental analyses. Bio actives having high GI absorption and bioavailability, following Lipinski rule of 5 and drug likeness score were considered for further analysis. [16,17].

Drug standardization and QC details –

The Hexane and Ethanolic extracts of *Hygrophila schulli* were subjected to qualitative analysis for the various Phytoconstituents like Alkaloids, Carbohydrates, Glycosides, Phytosterols, Saponins, Tannins, Proteins, Amino acids and Flavonoids). *Hygrophila schulli* seed extracts were subjected to various phytochemical tests for the presence of various classes of compounds. The tests exhibit the presence of different classes of compounds in all the extracts. Result of the tests performed confirmed presence of different class of compounds in most of the extracts.

Pharmacological Evaluation**Animals:**

This study was approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee, (Ethics approval no. ICP/IAEC/12-13/12). All experimental protocol followed the institutional guidelines for the care and use of laboratory animals.

Healthy Albino Wistar rats of either sex weighing between 150-200 gm and Swiss albino mice weighing 30-40 gm of either sex were procured from the National Toxicology Centre, Pune. The animals were housed under standard environmental conditions, including a temperature of $22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, humidity of $55 \pm 5\%$, and a 12-hour light/dark cycle. They were kept in polypropylene cages, with seven rats per cage, and had free access to water ad libitum.

Antihyperlipidemic Activity**High Fat Diet-Induced Hypercholesterolemia**

*H*Sethanolic and hexane extracts were evaluated using this model at a single dose of 500 mg/kg bw. A 500 mg/kg dose was typically chosen based on prior acute toxicity studies and empirical evidences demonstrating that this higher range effectively modulates lipid parameters in hyperlipidemic rodent models. The animals were divided into 9 groups of six animals each and were treated with vehicle, Atorvastatin (10mg/kg, po), HSE (500 mg/kg, po), HSH (500 mg/kg, po) respectively. All the animals and had free access to water.

Hyperlipidaemia was induced by allowing the animals to feed on a High Fat Diet formula devised by us: Wheat Flour-35%, Besan-15%, Sucrose-20%, Vanaspati Ghee-20%, Milk Powder -5%, Groundnut oil-51%, Multivitamin Tablet (Supradyn) 100gm.

The ingredients were mixed, and dough was rolled into round pellets, and were allowed to dry in oven. The animals were fed on this diet ad-libitum for 30 days. On the 30th day blood was withdrawn by retro orbital puncture and various anthropometrical parameters were estimated. Induction of Hyperlipidaemia was confirmed by estimation of lipid profile. For the next 30 days except for the normal control and disease control groups all other groups were treated

with the respective extracts along with high fat diet. The animals had access only to the high fat diet and free access to water. On the 60th day the animals were sacrificed by decapitation under mild anaesthesia. Blood was collected by the heart puncture method and again all the biochemical parameters were analysed. The liver was separated and liver homogenate was analysed for hepatic lipid levels[21].

4. RESULTS

Data mining for bioactives of HSseeds, their potential targets and hyperlipidemia targets

A total of 37 bioactive compound HS seeds were identified from Dr. Duke's Phytochemical and Ethnobotanical Database, Indian Medicinal Plants, Phytochemistry and Therapeutics (IMPPAT) and literature. We obtained drug canonical smile from PubChem.

Total 3417 targets of 37 bioactive compound were predicted using the Swiss Target Prediction servers with "Homo sapiens" limitations and after removing duplicates, 779 unique targets were obtained.

The 15, and 26 proteins involved in pathogenesis of hyperlipidaemia were retrieved from the String and Disgenet Database respectively confining the result to "Homo sapiens". After removing duplicates, a total 35 proteins were identified involved in Hyperlipidaemia.

779 unique targets of 37 bioactives of HS seeds were overlapped with 35 hyperlipidaemia targets using the VENN Bioinformatics Tools (Figure 2) to obtain 7 intersecting targets (APOB, LDLR, GCG, PPARA, ABCB1, NOS3, and ADRB2) referred to as the hyperlipidaemia related targets of HSseeds (HS-HL). Out of 37 bioactives of HSseeds, 26 bioactives were found interaction with 7 hyperlipidaemia related targets of HSseeds (Table 1)

Figure 1: Schematic workflow of the network pharmacology analysis of Bioactives against Hyperlipidemia

Fig.2: Identification of Hyperlipidaemia related targets of HSseeds (HS-HL)

Table 1: Topological parameters of PEL bioactives

Sr. no	Bioactives	Degree	Betweenness Centrality	Closeness Centrality	Topological Coefficient
1.	Betulin	7	0.194888	0.531646	0.27619
2.	Octadecanoic Acid	3	0.042941	0.451613	0.473118
3.	N-Hexadecanoic Acid	3	0.042941	0.451613	0.473118
4.	1-Nonadecene	3	0.033102	0.407767	0.371795
5.	Palmitic acid	3	0.042941	0.451613	0.473118
6.	Stearic acid	3	0.042941	0.451613	0.473118
7.	Oxiraneoctanoic Acid, 3-Octyl Cis	2	0.001659	0.378378	0.695652
8.	Octadec-9-Enoic Acid	2	0.001659	0.378378	0.695652
9.	9,12-Octadecadienoic Acid(z,z)-Methyl Ester	2	0.014673	0.4	0.538462
10.	Lysine	2	0.014475	0.4	0.557692
11.	Oleic acid	2	0.001659	0.378378	0.695652
12.	Apigenin-7-O-glucuronide	1	0	0.306569	0
13.	Squalene	1	0	0.371681	0
14.	Hexadecanoic Acid Ethyl Ester	1	0	0.371681	0
15.	1-Hexadecene	1	0	0.371681	0
16.	1-Tetradecene	1	0	0.371681	0
17.	Mannose	1	0	0.306569	0
18.	Glucose	1	0	0.306569	0
19.	Arabinose	1	0	0.306569	0
20.	Î²- sitosterol	1	0	0.371681	0
21.	Rhamnose	1	0	0.306569	0
22.	Glucuronic acid	1	0	0.306569	0

23. Myristic acid	1	0	0.371681	0
24. D-Xylose	1	0	0.306569	0
25. Linoleic acid	1	0	0.371681	0
26. Nicotinic acid	1	0	0.285714	0

Network construction and analysis

The PPI network of 7 hyperlipidemia related targets of HSseeds was made using STRING database. It consisted of 7 nodes and 11 edges with an average node degree of 3.14 (Figure 2).

Fig. 3: Protein-protein interaction network of Hyperlipidaemia related targets of HS seeds using STRING database

The network between bioactive present in HSseeds, hyperlipidaemia related targets of HS seeds and related KEGG pathway was established to explore the mechanism of action PHS seeds in hyperlipidaemia using Cytoscape version 3.9.1. The network consisted of 43 nodes and 68 edges. Here nodes include bioactive present in HS seeds (26 node), hyperlipidaemia related targets of HS seeds (7nodes) and related KEGG pathways (10 nodes), while edges indicate the interaction between these nodes. It was found that out of 37 bioactives of HS seeds, 26bio activesinteract with hyperlipidaemia related targets of HS seeds targets in the network as indicated by degree counts. Almost 11 bioactive of HS showed interaction with more than one Hyperlipidemia related targets indicating synergistic action of HS. Betulin, a triterpeneexhibited the highest interactions i.e.7with Hyperlipidemia related targetsincluding ABCB1, APOB, LDLR, GCG, PPARA, ADRB2, and NOS3. PPARA appeared as central node with 24 degree of freedom showing interaction with 6 pathways namely, Glucagon signalling pathway, Insulin resistance, cAMPsignalling pathway, Hepatitis C, Chemical carcinogenesis-receptor activation, and Diabetic cardiomyopathy and with 18 bioactives of HS namely Betulin, Stearic acid, Palmitic acid, Oleic acid, Linoleic acid, Myristic acid, β -sitosterol, Lysine, 1-Tetradecene, 1-Hexadecene, 1-Nonadecene, N-Hexadecanoic Acid, Hexadecanoic Acid Ethyl Ester, 9,12-Octadecadienoic Acid(z,z)-Methyl Ester, Octadec-9-Enoic Acid, Octadecanoic Acid, Oxiraneoctanoic Acid, 3-Octyl Cis, Squalene (Figure 3).

Fig 4: Bioactive-Targets-Pathway Network constructed using Cytoscape

Bioactive compounds of **KEG**
pathways

Pathway enrichment analysis revealed the top 10 pathways associated with the 7 targets using shinyGO which included Cholesterol metabolism, Bile secretion, Glucagon signaling pathway, Insulin resistance, Hepatitis C, cGMP-PKG signalling pathway, Diabetic cardiomyopathy, Lipid and atherosclerosis, Chemical carcinogenesis-receptor activation and cAMP signalling pathway. These pathways provide insights into the mechanisms potentially involved in Hyperlipidaemia treatment by *Hygrophilla schulliseeds* leaves active compound. Cholesterol metabolism pathway was found to be the most enriched pathway, while Lipid and atherosclerosis and CAMP signalling pathway were found to be associated with 3 out of 7 Hyperlipidemia related targets (figure 4 and table 2).

Fig 5: Pathway enrichment analysis

Table 2: Pathway-Associated Genes

Pathway	Genes
Cholesterol metabolism	APOB, LDLR
Bile secretion	LDLR, ABCB1
Glucagon signalling pathway	GCG, PPARA
Insulin resistance	NOS3, PPARA
Lipid and atherosclerosis	APOB, LDLR, NOS3
cAMPsignalling pathway	ADRB2, GCG, PPARA
Hepatitis C	LDLR, PPARA
cGMP-PKG signalling pathway	ADRB2, NOS3
Chemical carcinogenesis-receptor activation	ADRB2, PPARA
Diabetic cardiomyopathy	NOS3, PPARA

The hierarchical clustering of enriched pathways associated with *HS*bioactives in Hyperlipidemia was demonstrated in Figure 5. Pathways that are closely linked in biological functions tend to cluster together. Cholesterol metabolism and lipid & atherosclerosis are grouped, reinforcing their direct role in hyperlipidemia.

Fig 6: Dendrogram representing the hierarchical clustering of enriched pathways associated with *HS* bioactives in hyperlipidemia

Network between enriched pathways associated with HSbioactives in hyperlipidemia was shown in figure 6. Lipid and Atherosclerosis and cAMP Signaling Pathway were appeared to be largest nodes, suggesting its predominant role in hyperlipidemia. Lipid and Atherosclerosis pathway was found to be strongly linked to Cholesterol Metabolism as indicated by strong and most solid edge between the two.

Fig 7: Network graph between enriched pathways associated with *HS* bioactives in hyperlipidemia

Enrichment analysis of disease-gene associations revealed the most significant associations with Familial Hypercholesterolemia followed by Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Atherosclerosis, Myocardial Infarction, and Inherited Metabolic Disorder (Figure 7).

Table 4: Molecular docking results of Betulin

Ligand	Residue	Interaction type	Remark
Betulin	SER280	Hydrogen bond	Interacting with hydroxyl group
Betulin	CYS276	Hydrogen bond / polar contact	Shown near same hydroxyl region
Betulin	THR279	Polar contact	Nearby polar residue
Betulin	GLN277	Polar contact	Nearby polar residue
Betulin	CYS275	Hydrophobic contact	Pocket-lining residue
Betulin	ILE272	Hydrophobic contact	Pocket-lining residue
Betulin	VAL255	Hydrophobic contact	Pocket-lining residue
Betulin	LEU254	Hydrophobic contact	Pocket-lining residue
Betulin	ALA250	Hydrophobic contact	Pocket-lining residue
Betulin	ILE241	Hydrophobic contact	Pocket-lining residue
Betulin	LEU247	Hydrophobic contact	Pocket-lining residue
Betulin	PHE343	Hydrophobic contact	Aromatic hydrophobic contact
Betulin	LEU344	Hydrophobic contact	Pocket-lining residue
Betulin	ILE339	Hydrophobic contact	Pocket-lining residue
Betulin	MET330	Hydrophobic contact	Pocket-lining residue
Betulin	LEU331	Hydrophobic contact	Pocket-lining residue
Betulin	VAL332	Hydrophobic contact	Pocket-lining residue
Betulin	ALA333	Hydrophobic contact	Pocket-lining residue
Betulin	ILE317	Hydrophobic contact	Pocket-lining residue
Betulin	PHE318	Hydrophobic contact	Aromatic hydrophobic contact
Betulin	LEU321	Hydrophobic contact	Pocket-lining residue
Betulin	ILE354	Hydrophobic contact	Pocket-lining residue
Betulin	MET355	Hydrophobic contact	Pocket-lining residue
Betulin	PHE359	Hydrophobic contact	Aromatic hydrophobic contact
Betulin	GLU251	Unfavorable/polar vicinity	Nearby acidic residue
Betulin	LYS358	Polar/charged vicinity	Nearby basic residue
Betulin	GLY337	Nearby residue	No clear specific interaction shown

ADME analysis

SwissADME prediction was carried out by using Swiss ADME tool on February 2025. Out of 37 bioactives of HS, 22 had high GI absorption. In bioavailability 36 bioactives have >0.50 except squalene. ADME and drug-likeness evaluation indicated that several major bioactive compounds, including betulin, β -sitosterol, squalene, and linoleic acid, demonstrated favourable pharmacokinetic properties and acceptable Lipinski rule compliance. These findings support their potential suitability for further pharmacological investigation.

Determination of various Physical constant values

Physical constants	<i>Hygrophila schulli</i> %
Loss on drying	0.8
Total Ash value	7.5
Acid insoluble ash value	4.5
Water soluble ash value	2.5
Alcohol-soluble extractive value	4.73
Water-soluble extractive value	2.31

Antihyperlipidemic activity

Antihyperlipidemic activity was evaluated using High Fat Diet-Induced Hypercholesterolemia model in rats. It was observed that the animals had elevated lipid levels after having the high Fat diet for 30 days (Figure 10). The biochemical analysis of the samples collected after 30 days of *Hygrophila schulli* seedextracts treatment in hyperlipidaemia induced animals revealed significant reduction the elevated lipid levels. The hexane extract was highly significant in lowering the triglycerides as well as Total cholesterol. The HDL ratio too which was found to be suppressed in the negative control was found to be elevated. The Hexane extract was more active than the standard drug in controlling the lipid levels as well as increasing the HDL ratio (Figure 11).

The Liver Cholesterol as well as the Liver triglyceride levels were lowered by both the extracts. The SGOT as well as SGPT levels too were lowered in comparison to the disease control. The Ethanolic as well as the hexane extract were effective in lowering hepatic lipid levels, but hexane extract at a dose of 500 mg/kg was more significant. This clearly indicated the ability of the plant to revert the fatty liver condition. (Figure 12)

Figure 10: Lipid Profile on 30th day of in High Fat Diet-Induced Hypercholesterolemia

Table 5. Lipid Profile on 30th day of in High Fat Diet-Induced Hypercholesterolemia

Groups	TG mg%	TC mg%	HDL mg%	LDL mg%	VLDL mg%
Normal	83.67 ± 6.89	76.17 ± 4.31	34.17 ± 3.06	25.27 ± 4.81	16.73 ± 1.38
Negative control	125 ± 11.83	98.33 ± 6.12	40.5 ± 8.78	32.83 ± 12.97	25.00 ± 2.37
STD	131.67 ± 14.53	94.58 ± 4.82	35.33 ± 5.09	32.92 ± 6.03	26.33 ± 2.91
HSE	117.17 ± 20.12	88.17 ± 4.22	38.17 ± 5.12	26.57 ± 5.18	23.43 ± 4.02
HSH	113.33 ± 17.68	87.67 ± 7.53	35.33 ± 5.43	29.67 ± 13.90	22.67 ± 3.54

Data represented as Mean ± S.E.M. (n =6). All Values are expressed as mg/dl.

Figure 11: Lipid Profile on 60th day in *H. schulli* treated animals in High fat diet fed animals after 30 days treatment

Table 6. Lipid Profile on 60th day in *H. schulli* treated animals in High fat diet fed animals after 30 days treatment

HS	TGL mg%	TC mg%	HDL mg%	LDL mg%	VLDL mg%	HDL ratio
Normal 1%CMC	79.05 ±7.76	75.17 ±6.59	37.50 ± 3.27	21.86 ±7.83	15.81 ±1.55	49.89
Negative control	148.79 ±10.54	119.50 ±10.70	38.55 ±5.99	51.19 ±7.88	29.76 ±2.11	32.26
STD Atorvastatin	85.13 ±9.39***	85.34 ±10.90**	41.22 ±7.06***	27.10 ±6.45***	17.03 ±1.88***	48.30***
HSE 500 mg/kg	88.96 ±11.07**	76.93 ±6.48***	34.37 ±9.14**	24.78 ±5.54**	17.79 ±2.21***	44.67**
HSH 500 mg/kg	78.50 ±8.84***	72.08 ±3.88***	37.80 ±5.88***	18.58 ±6.40***	15.70 ±1.77***	52.44***

Data represented as Mean ± S.E.M. (n =6). All Values are expressed as mg/dl. *** P < 0.0001, ** P < 0.05, NS – Not Significant when compared to Negative control.

Figure 12: SGOT, SGPT & Liver Lipid Levels on 60th day post treatment by *H.schulli*

Table 7. SGOT, SGPT & Liver Lipid Levels on 60th day post treatment by *H. schulli*

	L -TC mg%	L-TGL mg%	SGPT mg%	SGOT mg%
Normal	89.67 ± 4.49	152.67 ± 11.62	53.50 ± 6.36	193.50 ± 10.67
Negative Control	141.83 ± 9.33	263.67 ± 13.20	76.33 ± 5.53	225.33 ± 9.67
STD Atorvastatin	72.17 ± 15.22***	161.83 ± 12.41***	58.17 ± 1.36***	169.00 ± 7.75***
HSE 500mg/kg	83.50 ± 8.53***	173.00 ± 15.79***	61.67 ± 7.40***	188.00 ± 5.49***
HSH 500mg/kg	76.33 ± 5.61***	166.8 ± 14.65***	62.83 ± 6.27***	190.2 ± 6.85**

Data represented as Mean ± S.E.M. (n =6). All Values are expressed as mg/dl.

*** P < 0.0001, ** P < 0.05, NS – Not Significant when compared to Negative control

5. DISCUSSION

Hyperlipidemia, is a well-known worldwide disaster with prevalence of 33.8 %, and is related to various lethal diseases, including myocardial infarction, stroke, etc.[22]. Currently, exploring natural medicines for the treatment of hyperlipidemia is of more importance, knowing that lovastatin, the first statin approved and marketed by FDA in 1987 have been derived from natural source, the fungus *Aspergillus terreus*[23]. This remarkable success of

the using natural products to discover new hypolipidemic agents made us explore the lipid-lowering potential of *Hygrophila schulli* seed bioactives.

Network pharmacology is an evolving revolutionary method in the drug discovery process based on systems biology and multifaceted pharmacology [24]. Network pharmacology uses various bioinformatics tools and databases to identify the mechanism of pharmacological action of compounds. In recent years many researchers have used network pharmacological approaches to predict probable mechanisms of herbal bioactives and or ayurvedic composites useful in therapeutics [25]. The network pharmacology is based on network build on associations between drugs/ bioactives, their targets, diseases, and signalling pathways to know the effects of drugs and there contribute in new drug development [26]. Thus, in this study, we attempted to explore bioactive compounds of *Hygrophila schulli* seed, their molecular targets, and their contribution to hyperlipidemia using, network pharmacology approach and its experimental validation.

We retrieved 37 bioactive compounds of *Hygrophila schulli* seed and 779 targets. Seven hyperlipidaemia related targets *Hygrophila schulli* seeds (APOB, LDLR, GCG, PPARA, ABCB1, NOS3, and ADRB2) were identified overlapping with 35 hyperlipidaemia proteins. These seven intersected hyperlipidaemia related targets *Hygrophila schulli* seeds represent key molecular nodes where *H. schulli* might exert its therapeutic effects in hyperlipidaemia. 26 bioactives of *Hygrophila schulli* seeds were identified interacting with 7 hyperlipidemia related targets of HS seeds [Figure no-2]. The analysis based on topological parameters viz, Degree, Betweenness Centrality, Closeness Centrality, and Topological Coefficient endorsed Betulin as a key bioactive with high degree, betweenness, and closeness centrality, modulating hyperlipidemia-related pathways. Pathway enrichment analysis predicted 10 enriched signalling pathways involved in pathogenesis of hyperlipidemia namely, Cholesterol metabolism, Bile secretion, Glucagon Signaling pathway, Insulin resistance, Hepatitis C, cGMP-PKG Signaling pathway, Diabetic cardiomyopathy, Lipid and atherosclerosis, Chemical carcinogenesis-receptor activation and cAMP Signaling pathway. Hierarchical clustering of the enriched pathways showed functional associations, where cholesterol metabolism was closest to lipid and atherosclerosis, and insulin resistance was clustered with cAMP and cGMP-PKG Signaling. These pathways are connected with cardiovascular protection, regulation of glucose metabolism, and augmentation of endothelial function, further supporting the therapeutic potential of *Hygrophila schulli* for hyperlipidemia and related metabolic disease [27]. In particular, the clustering of insulin resistance and diabetic cardiomyopathy validates that therapeutic efficacy of *Hygrophila schulli* may also exist independent of lipid modulation, with potential to manage diabetes and prevent cardiovascular disease [28].

Apolipoprotein B (ApoB) is a well-known lipoprotein involved in atherogenesis, major cause of cardiovascular disease like hypercholesterolemia [29]. In this study, APOB appeared as a major hub in this PPI network, interacting with LDLR, NOS3, ADRB2, PPARA, and GCG, which suggest that *Hygrophila schulli* may modulate lipid metabolism by influencing APOB expression or function. Network analysis advocate that Betulin and 1-Nonadecene interact with APOB via modulation of Cholesterol metabolism and Lipid and atherosclerosis pathway. It has been known that diminished Low-Density Lipoprotein Receptor (LDLR) activity due to genetic mutations causes exceedingly raised serum LDL levels, which initiates early onset of atherosclerosis in familial hypercholesterolemia (FH). Therefore, LDLR may be looked as targets for development of novel therapeutic for combined familial hyperlipidemia [30]. LDLR is vital in lipid metabolism by facilitating the uptake of cholesterol-rich lipoproteins, particularly LDL, from the bloodstream into cells, thereby regulating cholesterol levels and preventing its accumulation [30].

The alteration of peroxisome proliferator activated receptors (PPARs) activity have been found to reduce risk factors associated with metabolic disorders, making them a reliable target metabolic syndrome including hyperlipidemia. Hypolipidemic action of fibrates has been mediated through PPAR on lipid and lipoprotein metabolism [31].

Nitric oxide synthase 3 (NOS3) plays a role in lipid metabolism, with studies showing that NOS3 deficiency or inhibition can lead to increased hepatic lipid synthesis and decreased fatty acid oxidation, suggesting a role in regulating lipid content. NOS3 overexpression increases expression of peroxisome proliferator activated receptor (PPAR)- α , which is known to regulate lipid metabolism [32,33].

In the present study, seven hyperlipidemia related targets *Hygrophila schulli* seeds (APOB, LDLR, GCG, PPARA, ABCB1, NOS3, and ADRB2) were identified overlapping with 35 hyperlipidemia proteins. Further, STRING enrichment analysis identified the central position of LDLR, APOB, PPARA, and NOS3 in hyperlipidemia regulation. LDLR (Low-Density Lipoprotein Receptor) and APOB (Apolipoprotein B) are central to lipid transport and cholesterol metabolism because they directly participate in lipid storage and clearance of LDL [34]. PPARA (Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor Alpha), by contrast, has been directly linked with insulin resistance and lipid oxidation [35]. Lastly, NOS3 (Endothelial Nitric Oxide Synthase 3) is mapped to increased hepatic lipid synthesis and decreased fatty acid oxidation, suggesting a role in regulating lipid content [32].

In addition, network analysis revealed that various bioactive interact with multiple key target proteins, which in turn influence critical signalling pathways suggesting polypharmacological properties in lipid metabolism and thereby in hyperlipidemia. 18 bioactive compounds namely 1-Hexadecene, 1-Nonadecene, 1-Tetradecene, 9,12-Octadecadienoic Acid(z,z)-Methyl Ester, Betulin, Hexadecanoic Acid Ethyl Ester, Linoleic acid, Lysine, Myristic acid, N-Hexadecanoic Acid, Octadec-9-Enoic Acid, Octadecanoic Acid, Oleic acid, Oxiraneoctanoic Acid, 3-Octyl Cis, Palmitic acid, Squalene, Stearic acid, β - sitosterol were found to interact with PPARA directly linked with insulin resistance and cAMP Signaling pathway. Two bioactive namely 1-Nonadecene and Betulin was found to interact with APOB linked to highly enriched Cholesterol metabolism and Lipid and atherosclerosis pathway involved in lipid transport and cholesterol metabolism. Two bioactives namely 9,12-Octadecadienoic Acid(z,z)-Methyl Ester and Betulin were found to interact with LDLR linked to Bile secretion Cholesterol metabolism Hepatitis C and Lipid and atherosclerosis pathway contributing to LDL clearance and thus to hyperlipidemia. Betulin, Lysine and Nicotinic acid were found to interact with NOS3 via cGMP-PKG Signaling pathway, Diabetic cardiomyopathy, Insulin resistance and Lipid and atherosclerosis pathway.

Betulin showed two clear hydrogen-bond interaction with SER280 and CYS276. The ligand was predominantly stabilized by extensive hydrophobic interactions with residues including ILE272, LEU254, LEU247, PHE343, LEU344, ILE317, PHE318, LEU321, ILE354, and MET355, indicating that binding is mainly driven by hydrophobic pocket complementarity.

Overall it can be resolved that Betulin, Octadecanoic Acid, N-Hexadecanoic Acid, 1-Nonadecene, Palmitic acid and Stearic acid are the main bioactive compound found to interact with more than two key targets of hyperlipidemia.

Furthermore, disease-gene association analysis showed strong associations of these key targets with familial hypercholesterolemia, atherosclerosis, myocardial infarction, type 2 diabetes mellitus, and inherited metabolic disorders. Thus, this intimate association of key target genes with metabolic disorders and interaction of various bioactives with multiple key targets suggests the therapeutic potential of *Hygrophila schulli* in the management of hyperlipidemia and cardiovascular disease by multi-targeting mechanisms.

Supplementary in vivo experiments presented strong evidence for *Hygrophila schulli* seed extract lipid-lowering activity. Most importantly, the hexane extract caused a significant decrease in triglyceride and total cholesterol levels, even exceeding the control lipid-lowering drug [34,35]. Moreover, the suppressed levels of HDL in disease group were normalized upon treatment, indicating improvement in lipoprotein balance and cardiovascular status. The drastic decrease in liver cholesterol and triglyceride levels further indicated a hepatoprotective effect, which was further corroborated by the decreased levels of SGOT and SGPT, major markers of liver function. The hexane extract at 500 mg/kg showed the highest efficacy, showing dose response and potential for reversing fatty liver status.

These findings demonstrate the multi-targeted therapeutic potential of *Hygrophila schulli* bioactives as a novel, natural remedy over traditional lipid-lowering drugs with reduced adverse effects and is therefore an ideal candidate for Antihyperlipidemic therapy.

6. CONCLUSION

In the present study, we investigated and validated the therapeutic potential of *Hygrophila schulli* (HS) seed bioactives in hyperlipidemia using an integrated approach of network pharmacology with experimental confirmation. Total of 26 bioactives were identified interacting with seven hyperlipidemia-related targets namely, APOB, LDLR, GCG, PPARA, ABCB1, NOS3, ADRB2. Disease-gene association analysis supports the association of these targets in hyperlipidemia and cardiovascular diseases Network analysis identified Betulin as a key bioactive altering lipid metabolism via manysignalling pathways, including cholesterol metabolism, cAMP Signaling pathway, and insulin resistance. Further, in vivo experimental findings in high fat diet induced hyperlipidemia model endorsed the antihyperlipidemic potential of HS seed extracts, indicated by reduction in triglycerides, total cholesterol and increased HDL levels with the hexane extract of HS seed along with hepatoprotective effects by reduction liver cholesterol and triglycerides. Thus, the results of present study suggest HS seed bioactives as multi-targeted promising natural therapeutic for hyperlipidemia treatment, possibly providing safer and effective alternative for management of lipid disorders and associated metabolic diseases.

AI Declaration

No generative artificial intelligence tools were used for the generation of scientific results, data analysis, or figure preparation in this study. Any language editing assistance was limited to grammar correction, and the authors take full responsibility for the integrity of the manuscript.

Conflict of Interest – The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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